

Business Strategy Formulation for PT Silka Teguh Sejahtera (Sciencom) to Elevate its Revenue

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ABSTRACT: PT Silka Teguh Sejahtera (Sciencom) is one of Indonesia's IT and computer training providers. In the past several years, the company faces limited revenue growth despite its strong reputation and high-quality training services as well as promising market potential for IT and computer training provider. This happens because Sciencom main target customer base is government institutions which have faced budget reductions for education and training. This study aims to formulate a business strategy for Sciencom to enhance its revenue by identifying the factors influencing the limited growth of the company's revenue. The primary data is gathered from qualitative method in which the author conducted interviews with Sciencom's employees and customers representatives in order to analyze the internal and external factors to the business issue. To support the finding, the author uses secondary data collected from company's reports, journals, books, and websites. Through thorough internal and external analysis, the author was able to propose a new Segmentation, Targeting, and Positioning (STP) and Marketing Mix 7Ps to develop Sciencom's business strategy using the Ansoff Matrix Growth Strategy that the company can utilize in order to elevate its revenue amidst a competitive market. The proposed strategy include expanding the target customer base to state-owned enterprises and fresh graduates, integrating a Learning Management System (LMS) for online training, offering ERP solutions, partnering with universities for Swakelola Type 2 projects, forming a digital marketing and human resources departments, and regularly updating IT courses, certification, and promotional package offerings.

KEYWORDS: Business Strategy, IT Training, Marketing Mix 7Ps, Revenue Growth, Sciencom, Segmentation Targeting and Positioning (STP)

INTRODUCTION

In the contemporary landscape of business competition, organizations are compelled to continuously explore innovative methods and strategies to gain a competitive edge in their respective domains (Schymik, 2018). Strategy plays a pivotal role in achieving organizational objectives, involving the strategic allocation and utilization of crucial resources to meet these goals (Syamsuri & Amril, 2022). Effective strategy formulation requires the integration of internal resources with a comprehensive external analysis of industry structures (Rokhayati, Sholihin, Supriyadi, & Nahartyo, 2021). By leveraging internal resources in conjunction with an external industry assessment, organizations can derive various competitive advantages (Farida & Setiawan, 2022). A well-defined strategy provides coherence in decision-making across the organization and over time, functioning as a heuristic framework to guide daily operations.

Businesses can utilize a variety of strategies to enhance revenue, such as expanding their product and service offerings, exploring new markets, and increasing marketing and sales efforts. Broadening the range of products and services can drive revenue growth by giving consumers more options. This might involve developing new products, modifying existing ones, or creating bundles. Additionally, intensifying marketing and sales activities can attract a wider audience and boost sales. This could involve increased investment in marketing, improving sales efficiency, or offering promotions and discounts. Furthermore, exploring opportunities in untapped areas, such as expanding geographically or targeting new customer segments, can also maximize revenue (Rakhsitha, et al., 2023).

Indonesia is currently focused on economic recovery post-COVID-19, where high productivity in all sectors is an important note for the government. In this regard, the digital ecosystem's readiness is crucial for restoring the productivity of national economic sectors (Kominfo, 2021). Hence, it is evident that digital transformation, intrinsic to Industry 4.0, is the key to business opportunities and one of the strategies toward the attainment of Indonesia's Vision 2045 (Ministry of National Development Planning/Bappenas, 2023). Nevertheless, the large challenge for the country in developing a sufficient digital talent pool is that by 2030, the number of

required digital talents will have reached 9 million, which is an additional 600,000 new digital experts yearly (CNBC Indonesia, 2022).

The service providers, according to Rogala et al. (2017), encompass both businesses and private persons who provide educational services outside of the official school system. Based on UU No. 20 Tahun 2003 about the National Education System, the non-formal education and skills training system in Indonesia is defined as an educational pathway that functions outside of the official system and is set up in a systematic, hierarchical manner. Non-formal education is essential for fostering the kinds of talents that propel economic growth one of which is the IT sector (Suryono & Tohani, 2016).

Information technology involves the process of computers managing information based on commands from software (Collins B., 2002). In today's digital era, proficiency in Information and Communication Technology (ICT) is essential (Elhazzam, 2015). In 2015, Indonesia hosts approximately 20,000 private training providers, offering brief courses aimed at swiftly preparing participants for employment or entrepreneurship (Skjaerlund & Loop, 2015).

Despite promising market potential, PT Silka Teguh Sejahtera, an Indonesian IT and computer training provider, has limited revenue growth within the last five years. The “5 whys” analysis (Figure 1) shows the root cause of this situation derived from limited range of existing client that focused on government entities, while the private and state-owned companies that was not beneficiary to Sciencom. The government institutions, the main target customer of Sciencom, has budget allocation for training sourced from state budget. Unfortunately, the state budget has been reallocated to infrastructure development, health, social aid programs, and public education (Ministry of Finance, 2023).

Figure 1. The 5 Whys Analysis of Sciencom's Business Issue
Source: The Author Interview with Stakeholders and Analysis

This study aims to develop a business strategy to enhance Sciencom's revenue by identifying and addressing the factors limiting its growth. The key question on this research namely:

1. What are the internal and external factors that contribute to the limited growth of Sciencom's revenue?
2. What potential strategies can be proposed to address the issue of Sciencom's limited revenue growth?

METHODOLOGY

This research employs qualitative methodology to analyze external threats and opportunities, alongside internal strengths and weaknesses, facilitating the development of a new business strategy for Sciencom. Utilizing the Analyze Formulate Implement (AFI) strategy framework, the study conducts analysis of both internal and external factors relevant to Sciencom's business context, based on primary and secondary data.

Primary data collected through semi-structured interviews with three of Sciencom's employees and five decision-makers from its client base, responsible for IT and computer training within their organizations. Per case study, Creswell (2013) recommends to interview between three to five persons. These interviews featured open-ended questions to encourage detailed discussions and capture wide spectrum of insights (Dörnyei, 2007; Alamri, 2019). Secondary data sourced from company reports, academic journals, books, and websites

Interviews with Sciencom employees were not recorded to ensure confidentiality, but detailed notes are taken during the interviews. On the other hand, following the interviews with Sciencom's customers, the audios were transcribed into written text. The inductive coding process is then used to create codes based on the actual data, which allowed the analysis to naturally reflect the discussions (Vears & Gillam, 2022). The qualitative data then processed by using content analysis according to Mayring (2014), in which content analysis is defined as systematically classifying textual data into categories to explore behaviors and thoughts related to the information (Hsieh & Shannon, 2005; Zhang & Wildemuth, 2009).

The internal analysis was conducted using the Porter's Value Chain, Segmentation, Targeting, Positioning (STP), and the Marketing Mix 7Ps, identifying Sciencom's strengths and weaknesses. Conversely, the external analysis was carried out using Political Economic Social Technology Environment Legal (PESTEL) analysis, Porter's Five Forces, competitor analysis, and customer analysis, identifying factors that could impact Sciencom. The combination of these analyses provided an understanding of the underlying condition, which facilitated the formulation of a new business strategy. This strategy proposes revised STP and Marketing Mix 7Ps for Sciencom, guided by insights derived from SWOT and TOWS analyses. Finally, these proposed marketing strategies outline the business strategy that Sciencom will implement based on Ansoff Matrix.

Figure 2. Research Framework
Source: Author Analysis

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

A. External Analysis

PESTEL Analysis

Every business function within a larger macro-environment made up several components: political factors, economic conditions, sociocultural forces, technological factors, environmental factors, and legal/regulatory factors, as described by (Thompson, Peteraf, Gamble, & Strickland III, 2018). PESTEL analysis refers to tools for the analysis and monitoring of the external environment in which the organization operates (Christodoulou & Cullinane, 2019).

For political aspect, the Government of Indonesia has reallocated the state budget, prioritizing sectors such as infrastructure, healthcare social programs, and education (Ministry of Finance, 2023). A primary challenge for government institutions is the resource constraint from a budgetary perspective, which severely limits their ability to enhance civil servant competencies (Sinurat, 2022). Consequently, this shift has significantly reduced funding available for professional training, directly impacting Sciencom's operations. For economic aspect, Bank Indonesia forecasts an economic growth rate between 4.7% and 5.5% for 2024 (CNN Indonesia, 2023). The digital sector contributed approximately Rp392 trillion to the economy up to 2020 (Ministry of Communication and Informatics, 2020). Leveraging this momentum, the digital economy is projected to support national economic growth of 5.4% to 6.2% by 2045. This surge in digital growth offers Sciencom significant opportunities to expand its customer base and increase revenue by meeting the escalating demand for IT and computer training. For social aspects, significant skills gap exists, with an estimated need for 9 million trained workers by 2030 (World Bank, 2018). LinkedIn has released research stated that 43% of companies in various countries, including Indonesia, are seeking employee candidates aged 18-47 years old that has several skills like problem solving, AI, IT & web, critical thinking, and communication skills (Wulandari, 2024). Companies that specializing in digital skills have experienced a significant growth in traffic and revenue (Ramli, 2022). For technological aspect, the advancements in Artificial Intelligence (AI), Machine Learning (ML), Big Data, and cyber security underscore the growing demand for IT training (Johnson, et al., 2021; Bharadiya, 2023; Ministry of Finance, 2021). Furthermore, currently, the adoption of Learning Management Systems and Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP) solutions has been popular among education and business sectors, respectively (Esawe, et al., 2023; Witjaksono, et al., 2021). For environmental aspect, the technology-related industries emit more than the air transport industry, and it accounts for about 1% of the world's greenhouse gases, which will grow to 14% by the year 2040 (Belkhir & Emeligi, 2018; Lanchaster University, 2021; McKinsey & Company, 2022). E-learning, however, tending to have a lowered carbon footprint since less travel and paper will need to be used, hence, making online education more sustainable (Roy, Potter, & Yarrow, 2008). For legal aspect, Sciencom is accredited by Lembaga Sertifikasi Profesi, Telematika and certified by EC-Council so as to meet industrial requirements. Materials used for training at Sciencom refer to Peraturan Presiden Republik Indonesia Nomor 95 Tahun 2019, promoting digital transformation in government services. The Ministerial Regulation of State-Owned Enterprises (Permen BUMN Number PER-09/MBU/2012) adopts the COBIT framework for IT governance, presenting an opportunity for Sciencom to offer COBIT training to state-owned enterprises.

Porter's Five Forces

Porter's Five Forces describes how there exist five (the intensity of rivalry among existing competitors, the threat of new entrants, the threat from substitute products or services, the bargaining power of suppliers and last but not least, the bargaining power of customers) different forces which affect every industry, defining the outlook of its competitiveness and finally, defining the profitability of the sector (Porter, 2008).

The rivalry among existing competitors in the IT training industry is high since it is estimated 20,000 private training providers, including 22 computer training providers registered in DKI Province (Skjaerlund & Loop, 2015). Similar course offerings and pricing disparities make it easy for customers to switch providers although Sciencom has a strong reputation and loyal customer among government institutions. The threat of new entrants is considered to be moderate. Digital skills are fast-growing, and avenues are open to new entrants. Even though setting up an online platform is relatively quite cheap, but a physical training center may involve a little more in terms of expenses. Moreover, building a reputation, credibility, and getting accreditation is also quite challenging and involves huge expenses—an added advantage to Sciencom with already established customer loyalty in government institutions. The threat of substitute products or service can be categorized as moderate because although e-learning platform is conveniently accessible, but the need of traditional face-to-face learning method is still high because its offer more interactive and immediate aid from instructions. The bargaining power of suppliers is low. Sciencom's suppliers are the freelance trainers, hotel

vendors, restaurants, and car rental agencies. The freelance trainers have moderate bargaining power because of the presence of certain requirements needed to be met as requirement by the company. This can be minimized if the company has linkages with some educational institutions to supply qualified trainers. The hotels, restaurants, and car rental agencies, on the other hand, have a low bargaining power because of the presence of comparable suppliers in their categories. Lastly, the bargaining power of buyers is considered high. Government institution clients are not easy to switch to other providers, but these customers might want to cancel training activities in case of changes in budget allocation. On the other hand, private and state-owned companies often seek the cheapest providers, increasing their bargaining power.

Competitor Analysis

Competitor analysis is crucial for a firm as it enables the preparation of anticipatory responses by collecting data and information on competitors' objectives, strategies, assumptions, and capabilities (Hitt et al., 2019). Several Sciencom's competitors according to the interview are ID-Networkers, NetCampus Training Center, and Brainmatics. Sciencom, the oldest IT and computer training provider among its competitors, offers a wide range of IT and computer training courses to differentiate its offering with competitors and the same thing goes to ID-Networkers, NetCampus Training Center, and Brainmatics. Despite having limited certification partnerships compares to competitors, Sciencom provides necessary certifications through temporary collaborations so that the company can compliance with industry standards and customer expectations. Notably, while competitors offer training across online, offline, and hybrid formats extensively utilizing Learning Management Systems (LMS) for both retail and corporate clients, Sciencom primarily delivers its training offline or through hybrid formats using Zoom, but only targets corporate clients where it could potentially missing out on the broader retail market. A unique aspect of Sciencom is its edutainment approach, which customizes courses to make learning enjoyable and guarantees repeat training if clients are dissatisfied. Additionally, it provides post-training reports aligned with government requirements. In terms of pricing, Sciencom adopts a premium strategy, with course fees significantly higher than those of its competitors, ranging from IDR 6,000,000 to IDR 38,000,000, compared to IDR 2,000,000 to IDR 13,740,000 charged by its competitors. This high-cost structure positions Sciencom at the upper end of the market, potentially limiting its accessibility to individuals and organizations with smaller training budgets. Sciencom has a strategically located training facility but only one physical center facility, compared to competitors with multiple offline locations. Aside from that, marketing of Sciencom relies on traditional direct sales and its official website, whereas competitors use social media to engage a broader audience.

Customer Analysis

Customer analysis is to evaluate perceived customer value, enhancing the firm's ability to offer superior value. Building strong, lasting customer relationships is crucial for fostering satisfaction with goods and services, which in turn promotes customer engagement and loyalty, leading to profitable relationships (Kotler & Keller, 2021; Kotler, et al., 2021). The interviews with Sciencom's customers provided insights about their experiences with Sciencom. The feedback covered about product, pricing, place, promotion, people, process, and physical evidence.

- Product of Sciencom is known for its reliability and excellent service portfolio. It offers customized training that includes a mix of theory and practical exercises, which facilitates quick learning and immediate workplace application. Regular updates to course content ensure alignment with the latest IT trends. However, customers suggest that more creative proposals and the integration of AI and visual aids in training materials could further enhance satisfaction. Additionally, expanding the range of certifications could meet the growing demand for career-relevant qualifications. To enhance participant satisfaction, implementation of Rancangan Bangun Program Pembelajaran (RBPP) can make the learning objectives clearer. Certifications are valuable and recognized for career advancement, though some clients desire more in-demand certification options.
- Price of Sciencom's is flexible, generally aligning with market standards and fitting within customer budgets. While online training is perceived as pricey, offline training costs are considered reasonable for the quality provided. The company's willingness to negotiate creates tailored packages that accommodate financial constraints of various clients.
- Place of Sciencom's training facilities contributes to its accessibility, although some clients have raised concerns about travel distance and traffic. Sciencom's flexibility in venue selection and the high quality of its facilities are major advantages. Increasing social media activity is recommended to enhance visibility and attract a broader client base.

- Promotion relies heavily on personal selling through direct interactions and traditional methods like WhatsApp and flyers. While effective in maintaining relationships, expanding digital marketing efforts and utilizing modern promotional strategies could help reach a wider audience, especially younger demographics.
- People as trainers are competent, receiving advance CV reviews to ensure quality. Their formal, non-rushed teaching style suits participants' learning culture, though more interactive methods may be needed for Gen Z participants. The sales team is known for quick responsiveness, effective communication, and discipline, ensuring customer satisfaction through regular updates and prompt problem resolution.
- Process from registration to post-training is smooth, straightforward, and quick responses. Sciencom's registration and experience with government institutions facilitate easy coordination and payments. Flexible invoicing and well-managed training documents meet client requirements. Negotiations focus on facilities, training themes, and schedules, with minimal price negotiation required. Training sessions are conducted in a relaxed environment with engaging activities, but aligning ice-breaking activities with training material could further aid lesson retention.
- Physical Evidence including main facilities and alternative venues like hotels are noted for being conducive for learning. During the training in the H Tower, Sciencom provide good classroom with laptops or PCs, prayer room, coffee break area and other supporting facilities such as billiard and massage chairs. Training at hotels offers better facilities and food, with Sciencom selecting the best hotels within government rates.

B. Internal Analysis

Porter's Value Chain

A company's value chain outlines the primary activities that generate customer value and the support activities that enhance these primary activities (Thompson, Peteraf, Gamble, & Strickland III, 2018). Analyzing the value chain helps identify which operational components contribute to value creation and which do not (Hitt, Ireland, & Hoskisson, 2019).

Sciencom's value chain primary activities begin with inbound logistics, where these are managed carefully with a focus on procuring high-quality, customized souvenirs that enhance client experiences, setting a positive tone for the engagement. Daily operations are structured to uphold high standards, with daily activities running in regular work hour. These include regular updates to course offerings and proactive client feedback collection to ensure continuous improvement and relevance of the training programs. Sciencom's work environment supports employee well-being with amenities such as snacks and beverages, and regular meetings at divisional and company-wide levels to foster alignment and responsiveness. The distribution of Sciencom's services prioritizes client satisfaction, employing an Edutainment approach that makes learning both enjoyable and effective. Trainers are dedicated to equipping clients with necessary skills, and the customer service team actively monitors satisfaction, addressing any concerns swiftly, including offering free replacement training for dissatisfied clients. Marketing and sales efforts, led by a proactive sales team, focus on maintaining strong client relationships through direct communication, supported by traditional personal selling and an actively managed official website. The absence of a dedicated social media team has limited Sciencom's online presence, with social media updates handled occasionally by customer service.

The support activities at Sciencom play a crucial role in enhancing the effectiveness of the primary activities. Product R&D and technology development ensure that the course list is regularly updated to reflect market demands and the latest technological trends, maintaining the relevance and quality of the training programs. Sciencom does not have a dedicated HR department. Therefore, the recruitment and employee training are usually requested to the director, and he will evaluate for the requests. The procurement process is well-organized by the IT and Operational division (handles electronic goods) and the Customer Service division (manages non-electronic items). Requests are approved by the director to ensure that all procurement aligns with the company's needs and budget constraints.

Segmentation, Targeting, and Positioning (STP)

Segmentation, Targeting, and Positioning (STP) are crucial for businesses seeking to attract the right customers, compare its position with competitors, differentiate its brand, focus marketing efforts, develop new products, and also helps identify market opportunities by thoroughly examining and pinpointing potential new customer segments (Khandelwal, Jakhar, & Khandelwal, 2020).

Sciencom's segmentation includes their potential customers who require IT and computer training that based in Jakarta due to the location of its training facility (Table 1).

Table I. Sciencom’s Current Segmentation

<i>Segmentation</i>	<i>Type of Segmentation</i>	<i>Description</i>
Geographic	Region	Jakarta
Demographic	Gender	Male & Female
	Age	18 – 45 years old
	Occupation	Professionals or employees, educators, recent graduates, students
	Education level	High school graduates, vocational and diploma holders, undergraduate students, postgraduate students
	Income	Middle – High
	Industry	Government institutions, state-owned enterprises, private companies, educational institutions
	Company size	Small, medium, and large
Psychographic	Lifestyle	Tech enthusiast, active learners
Behavioural	Benefit sought	Career changers, gain a specific technical skills

Source: Author Interview with Sciencom’s Employees

Currently, Sciencom's target customer is the large government institution in Jakarta. Typical clients are 25 – 40-year-old employees bearing undergraduates and postgraduates degree seeking an enhancement of their technical skills or a career shift.

Sciencom positions itself to be the premium IT training in Jakarta, specialized and developing courses tailored to client's preference in facilities, food, location, and trainers. The firm will focus on making learning a synergy of education and entertainment so that not only clients will earn their IT skills, but participant will also be having enjoyment in the process of training.

Marketing Mix 7Ps

Based on STP, the company designs a vast marketing mix that includes four elements such as Product, Price, Promotion, and Place and specifically for service sector including three more Ps — People, Process, and Physical Evidence. The four Ps would focus on developing products to meet consumer needs, pricing them attractively, promoting their benefit over others, and making them available thereby at places convenient to purchase, whereas the three other elements are of strategic nature and have direct relations with a firm's performance regarding customer satisfaction (Yudelson, 1999; Akroush, 2011; Kotler & Armstrong, 2017). The current Marketing Mix 7P’s for Scincom is described below:

- Products include a wide range of IT training services across eight categories: application, networking, operating systems, database, design & multimedia, programming, IT management, and security. Courses range from 3 to 15 days and are designed for a minimum of ten participants, featuring certification options and customizable training packages like duration, location, souvenirs, and trainers choices. Their edutainment approach combines education with entertainment, and their notable "bootcamp" package adding a standout point offering.
- Price for access the course vary from Rp 6,000,000 to Rp 38,000,000, based on course complexity and duration, with discounts for larger groups. Sciencom also provides more affordable workshop options that allow for individual or small group participation.
- Place of training is primarily conducted at Sciencom’s well-equipped facility in The H Tower, Kuningan, Jakarta, conveniently located near LRT and Transjakarta stations. On the hand, the media that clients can access information and register for training via the Sciencom website or through direct sales contacts.
- Promotion utilizes a mix of sales promotions, personal selling, and limited digital marketing. Regular workshops and introductory classes for new courses are promoted mainly through their website and personal selling, which help maintain client relationships and provide updates on new offerings.

- People in Sciencom's key personnel include skilled trainers to design and deliver training courses, sales representatives for tailor training programs to client needs as well as maintain good customer relationships, and customer service staff responsible for logistical support and feedback collection.
- Process in acquiring training projects through direct appointments and tenders, involving detailed coordination from initial client engagement to final delivery and follow-up, ensuring personalized and efficient service.
- Physical evidence includes facilities like classrooms, a coffee area, entertainment zone, and prayer room. Participants receive a training kit with a notebook, pen, and flash drive containing course materials. Door prizes enhance the training experience, and training souvenirs are distributed on the final day along with attendance certificates.

C. SWOT Analysis and TOWS Matrix

From the external and internal analysis, the author can identify the SWOT analysis of Sciencom in which is shown as follows:

Strengths:

1. Uses edutainment training with practical exercises.
2. Constantly updates its course offerings.
3. Customize training packages to clients' needs where Sciencom guaranteeing if the services do not, the participants will be given free repeat training.
4. The training facility is accessible for employees and clients
5. Have a good reputation among government institutions.
6. The sales team maintains strong client relationships.
7. The trainers are not only experts of their fields but also excellent in breaking down really complicated concepts.

Weaknesses:

1. Sciencom's customers are primarily government institutions.
2. Even though Sciencom has social media, its digital presence is very minimal.
3. Does not have dedicated departments for human resources and digital marketing.
4. Sciencom depends on freelance trainers.
5. The high prices of Sciencom's training programs make it difficult to attract individual customers.

Opportunities:

1. Develop its own LMS platform
2. Expand target customers to include state-owned companies
3. The material can include AI applications to provide option tools for participants
4. The step-by-step procedure materials can be made more visuals.
5. Adding RBPP (Rancangan Bangun Program Pembelajaran) to the syllabus
6. Collaborate with the universities to run Swakelola Type 2 to minimize trainer bargaining power and obtain project from educational institutions.
7. Adding Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP) solutions

Threats:

1. Reduction in the State Budget (APBN) allocated for education and training initiatives can impact revenues of Sciencom.
2. The highly competitive IT training industry makes clients easily switch providers
3. Sciencom must constantly update course list, technology, certification offerings to keep up with rapid changes in ICT and retain customers
4. Future economic downturns can lead to reduced spending on Sciencom's services since training is often the first expense cut when corporations need to tighten their spending.

Following the determination of the SWOT analysis, TOWS matrix then can be created. The TOWS Matrix is a strategic tool for evaluating a company's market situation by aligning its strengths with weaknesses and opportunities with threats to help identify areas for improvement within the business (David & David, 2012). Table 2 indicates the TOWS Matrix for Sciencom.

Table II. Sciencom’s TOWS Matrix

<i>Strength – Opportunity (SO)</i>	<i>Strength – Threat (ST)</i>
SO 1. Enhance the edutainment training approach by integrating a LMS so that participants can access materials before and after training, tracking tests progress, receive e-certificate and feedback (S1O1).	ST 1. Highlight the edutainment training approach, customized training packages, and high-quality training to differentiate Sciencom from competitors (S1S3S5T2)
SO 2. Continuously update course offerings to include AI applications in the material for simpler and faster tool options beside the conventional application (S2O3)	ST 2. Invest in continuous curriculum development and training for trainers to keep up with the technology advancements (S7T3)
SO 3. Use the strong brand reputation and tailored training packages to promote COBIT 5, AI, ML, big data, and cyber security to state-owned enterprises to broaden customer base (S3S5O2)	
SO 4. Add training packages to include ERP solutions, where Sciencom offers other services from implementation, and maintenance (S3O5)	
SO 5. Trainers can add RBPP (Rancangan Bangun Program Pembelajaran) to the syllabus to further clarify learning objective and also make the step-by-step procedure to be more visuals (S7O5O4)	
<i>Weakness – Opportunity (WO)</i>	<i>Weakness – Threat (WT)</i>
WO 1. Partnership with educational institutions for Swakelola Type 2 projects to reduce reliance on freelance trainers and obtain more projects (W4O4)	WT 1. Make a specific team for digital marketing and improve digital marketing efforts in order to enhance client engagement and brand visibility among competitors (W2W3T2)
WO 2. Create basic-level training package for individual customers by leveraging the LMS to deliver the training online (W5O1)	WT 2. Create dedicated department for human resources to improve recruitment and staff training leading to better service delivery compares to competitors (W3T2)

Source: Author Analysis

D. Proposed Segmentation, Targeting, Positioning (STP)

Segmentation Expanding geographic segmentation to include all of Indonesia can boost Sciencom’s revenue. This expansion will be supported by LMS-based training, which caters to individual customers who prefer online learning for its flexibility (**Error! Reference source not found.**).

Table III. Sciencom’s New Customer Segmentation

<i>Segmentation</i>	<i>Type of Segmentation</i>	<i>Description</i>
Geographic	Region	Indonesia
Demographic	Gender	Male & Female
	Age	18 – 45 years old
	Occupation	Professionals or employees, educators, recent graduates, students
	Education level	High school graduates, vocational and diploma holders, undergraduate students, postgraduate students
	Income	Middle – High

	Industry	Government institutions, state-owned enterprises, private companies, educational institutions
	Company size	Small, medium, and large
Psychographic	Lifestyle	Tech enthusiast, active learners
Behavioural	Benefit sought	Career changers, gain a specific technical skills

Source: Author Analysis

Targeting to includes corporate clients (state-owned companies) and retail customers (fresh graduates) to reduce reliance on government institutions. Sciencom can plan to target SOEs in Jakarta with specialized training packages such as COBIT 5, AI, ML, big data, and cybersecurity. Sciencom’s strong reputation among government institutions, combined with its ability to customize training packages and its edutainment approach, positions it well to attract these new clients. With the PESTEL analysis, there is also an opportunity to target fresh college graduates; those around 22 years old who are just starting to enter the job market. The sciencom program will be in the business of offering IT and computer training at the entry level online with LMS platforms to meet the new labor force and its need for developing modern workplace competencies.

Table IV. Sciencom’s New Target Customer Base

Description	Target Market
Region	Indonesia
Age	22 – 40 years old
Gender	Male & Female
Occupation	Professionals or employees, recent graduate
Income	Middle – High
Educational level	Undergraduates and Postgraduate
Industry	Government institutions and state-owned enterprises
Company size	Large
Lifestyle	Tech enthusiast, active learners
Benefit sought	Gain a specific technical skill, career changers

Source: Author Analysis

Positioning, for government and state-owned enterprises, Sciencom positions itself as a premium provider of tailored IT training programs that combine education with entertainment, ensuring high engagement and effective learning. For entry-level IT practitioners, Sciencom markets itself as an experienced provider offering accessible online IT training use real world practical theories with fun learning activities designed to equip participants with practical skills for the modern workplace.

E. Proposed Marketing Mix 7Ps

Product of Sciencom is suggested to deliver in high-quality, customer-oriented IT and computer training services, featuring customizable course materials, trainers, and locations. It plans to integrate Learning Management System (LMS) to facilitate basic-level training packages tailored for fresh graduates, enhancing the accessibility of materials, tests, and recorded sessions online. Regularly updating course lists is needed as well as include include AI applications in the material during the training sessions, enhance the visual appeal of its materials in the class, and update its course list proposal design. Aligning ice-breaking activities with training materials could enhance participant engagement and retention. Adding Rancangan Bangun Program Pembelajaran (RBPP) to its syllabus is necessary for clearer learning objectives. Furthermore, Sciencom should expand its certification offerings to align with customer demands identified through periodic surveys conducted by the sales team. Lastly, Sciencom could also add Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP) solutions in which the company can give training, implementation software and maintenance to its product offerings.

Price of Sciencom employs a flexible pricing strategy, accommodating the budgetary constraints of corporate clients. For online training aimed at fresh graduates, Sciencom should benchmark against competitors to ensure competitive and market-aligned pricing. Introducing discounts during special occasions like Hari Pendidikan Nasional and paydays could also attract more individual customers.

Place of Sciencom's primary training facility is located at The H Tower in Kuningan, Jakarta, known for its accessibility. Sciencom's training can also be conducted at various locations based on client requests. Enhancing its digital presence on social media platforms such as Instagram and TikTok is targeted to reach younger demographics, supported by a newly formed digital marketing team.

Promotion of Sciencom must maintain its effective practice of personal selling through direct communication with clients. However, enhancing promotional efforts through digital marketing is crucial. Sciencom should increase its activity on Instagram and TikTok, and engage in paid partnerships with media influencers to reach a broader audience. Sales promotions could include free introductory workshops, discounts for group enrollments, and special offers during significant events.

People related Sciencom's trainers are experts in their fields, capable of delivering clear and engaging lessons. To better cater to individual customers (in which nowadays are usually Generation Z) through online training, Sciencom should ensure that its trainers are not only knowledgeable but also interactive. Continuous professional development for trainers is essential to keep them updated with the latest IT advancements. Apart from that, the sales and customer service teams are known for their excellent communication, responsiveness, and ability to meet client needs. As a recommendation, Sciencom could create a dedicated team for digital marketing with graphic design expertise so that can create appealing course offerings as well as enhance Sciencom's online presence. As a result, increasing brand visibility to potential customers and fostering stronger relationship with customer online. Furthermore, establishing a human resources department to improve staff recruitment and training would further enhance service delivery.

Process for direct appointment and tender projects are smooth, straightforward, and efficient, from project acquisition to training delivery. The company's flexible invoicing and well-managed training documentation are particularly appreciated by government clients. However, Sciencom should explore partnerships with educational institutions, like Institut Teknologi Bandung, for Swakelola Type 2 projects to reduce reliance on freelance trainers and secure more projects. The Swakelola process includes planning, preparation, implementation, monitoring and reporting, and accountability stages, following LKPP Regulation Number 11 of 2021 for planning and LKPP Regulation Number 3 of 2021 for other stages.

Physical Evidence Sciencom's training facilities are well-equipped and comfortable, supporting a conducive learning environment. Participants appreciate the quality of training kits, souvenirs, and facilities at both the H Tower and hotel venues. However, the training kits can be improved by the integration of an LMS platform in order to enhance the accessibility and organization of training materials.

F. Proposed Ansoff Matrix

The Ansoff Matrix outline four distinct growth strategies depending on whether the products or markets are new or existing (Verhoeven & Johnson, 2017). Each strategy has different risk level, where the sequence from the lowest to the highest risk is market penetration, market expansion, product development, and diversification (Loredana, 2016). Through the elaboration of the proposed STP and the Marketing Mix 7Ps, the Ansoff Matrix growth strategies for Sciencom is fall under market penetration, market development, and product development.

Market Penetration for Sciencom's primary market consists of government institutions. Despite budget cuts in the state budget for education and training, there are still untapped opportunities within these institutions, particularly those connected to educational sectors. By leveraging Swakelola Type 2 partnerships with educational institutions, Sciencom can penetrate deeper into this existing market. Emphasizing its strengths—such as a strong portfolio, exceptional service, customizable training packages, the edutainment training approach, and well-managed post-training documentation—Sciencom can differentiate itself from competitors and attract more government institutions.

Market Development Sciencom can broaden its target market to include state-owned enterprises (SOEs), in line with Permen BUMN Number 09/MBU/2012, which encourages SOEs to improve their IT governance using frameworks like COBIT. Sciencom already offers COBIT 5 training and can expand its offerings to include training on AI, ML, big data, and cybersecurity, capitalizing on the rising demand for these skills due to digital transformation and increasing cybersecurity threats. To address challenges from

the company's past history working with SOEs such as high competition, payment collection issues, and budget/time uncertainties in SOEs, Sciencom should:

1. Build strong networks with decision-makers in SOEs to facilitate smooth cooperation.
2. Offer high-end training packages in specialized areas (COBIT 5, AI, ML, big data, cybersecurity) that differentiate Sciencom from competitors.
3. Conduct market research by selling their IT training program to identify SOEs with sufficient time and budget allocations for training, ensuring profitable margins and less bureaucratic complexity.

Additionally, Sciencom can expand geographically by developing an LMS platform to offer online beginner-level IT training to retail customers across Indonesia, particularly targeting fresh graduates. Effective market research is crucial to understand this new segment, including pricing strategies, relevant IT courses, promotional packages, and methods to encourage repeat business and recommendations.

Product Development is set to broaden its product range to include online beginner-level IT training utilizing an LMS platform tailored for new graduates, alongside ERP training, implementation, and management services for governmental and state-owned company clients. This platform will also cater to corporate clients, offering pre- and post-training access to course materials, tracking of assessment scores, issuance of e-certificates, and collection of participant feedback. The integration of the LMS and the rollout of ERP solutions will require significant investment in both budget and expertise. Sciencom is committed to investing in these areas, recognizing them as critical to maintaining market competitiveness and meeting evolving customer needs.

CONCLUSION

Sciencom, one of the IT and computer training providers in Indonesia, has built a strong reputation and offered track records of high-quality training services but had limited growth in terms of revenue. The stagnation is fueled by several internal and external factors. Internal factors happen because of the narrow customer base mainly limited to government entities, minimum social media activity caused by not having digital marketing team, no human resource department, reliance on freelance trainers, and premium pricing that deters individual customers with smaller budgets. Externally, the company is influenced by its reliance on APBN allocations, high competition in the IT training industry, the fast pace of technological changes, and economic downturns that may lower training budgets.

To address these challenges, several strategies have been proposed. Expanding the target customer base to include state-owned companies and fresh graduates can diversify income sources. Integrating an LMS platform can facilitate online beginner-level IT training for retail customer bases and provide corporate clients with convenient access to training materials and progress tracking. An additional ERP solution to these offered by Sciencom could attract more corporate clients that require comprehensive training and software implementation with corresponding service maintenance. Cooperation with educational institutions in terms of projects on Swakelola Type 2 will decrease dependence on freelance trainers as well as opening a lot of new project opportunities. Digital marketing teams for better visibility of online presence, engaging more clients; human resource departments, making staff recruitment, training, and management easier. Lastly, keeping updated IT courses, certification offerings, and promotional packages based on the client's needs and market trends is a continuous process to maintain competitiveness.

LIMITATION AND FUTURE RESEARCH

The research conducted has the following problem limitations:

1. The research will investigate business strategy formulation, excluding the risks associated with developing these strategies.
2. As PT Silka Teguh Sejahtera is a private company, there are limitations in accessing extensive secondary data.
3. The focus of this research is specifically on IT and computer training in the IT sector.

Future research could further explore the impact of the business strategies proposed for Sciencom by analyzing how these strategies actually affect the company's revenue growth. This could involve collecting and examining data on Sciencom's performance before and after implementing strategies.

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